

Development of Plant Chemistry in the Indian Sub-continent

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The use of crude plant extracts in therapy was known in India in the remote past. There is ample proof of applications of various recipes of Indian herbs in curing many a malady and realisation of herbal charms led to the development of Ayurvedic system of medicine. The latter comprises an important part of *Atharva Veda*, the most ancient treatise of Hindu medicine (1000 B.C.), viz., *Charak* and *Susruta Samhita* (written not later than 300-200 B.C.), which constitute two important sections of Ayurveda and deal with drug plants of ancient India. These volumes are considered to be monumental works towards our knowledge of science and art of healing.

From the Vedic period down to the Mohammedan invasion of India, Hindu medicine made a remarkable progress and permeated into Egypt, Greece and Rome, Arabia and Persia. This phytotherapy further flourished during the reign of Ashoke the Great, when many exotic plants were naturalised in this country (274-232 B.C.). The Emperor Ashoke sent the Buddhist monks to remote parts of the world to preach Buddhism. They carried medicinal plants with them for their own use and on their way back to India collected many new plants. These botanical specimens have now been naturalised, thus enriching the Indian flora.

Foreign influence on the study of Indian plants dates back to the 16th century when Portugese and Dutch scientists came to India. They took interest in the study of vegetable drugs and published many books of which "Hortus Malabaricus" written by Van Rheedes in 12 volumes (A.D. 1678-1703) is a valuable contribution.

With the advent of Western therapy in this country, glories of Ayurvedic medicine rapidly declined. It was later realised that Indigenous system of therapy should be revived from economic consideration. In the early part of the nineteenth century, a great campaign was started for restoring the old system of Ayurvedic medicine. William Jones, John Flemming, W. Roxburgh and W. Ainslie and others were active participants. They published several books on "Medicinal Herbs" of India and could make the people understand that India with variabilities of climate is a rich nursery in the world botany and this nursery is a big store-house of medicine. Thus, the importance of phytochemistry was recognised by Eastern as well as by Western scholars. But it was not possible to carry on research on Plant Chemistry on sound scientific basis till the end of the last century when scientific methods and techniques became available to the investigators'.

The first chemist to investigate plant products in India was W. O. Shaugnessy (1840) of Calcutta Medical College. Studies on medicinal and poisonous plants of India were later undertaken with right earnest in the same Institution by Warden and Hooper and they were the first to isolate arbin and a toxic protein, the poisonous principles of *Arbus precac-*

torius (kunch). These workers compiled an authoritative book on Indian drugs, 'Pharmacographia Indica', in collaboration with W. Dymock (1890-1899). Simultaneously many other important books appeared, of which the following ones are worthy of mention:

- (a) *Materia Medica of the Hindus* by U. C. Dutta (1870).
- (b) *A Dictionary of the Economic Products of India* by George Watt (1889-1893).
- (c) *Indigenous Drugs of India* by K. L. Dey (1896).
- (d) *Indian Medicinal Plants, Vols. I and II* by K. R. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu (1918).

In 1896, E. J. Hill² in Allahabad isolated the colouring matter of *Nyctanthes arbor-tris* Linn. and studied its properties. During the period 1912-1924, much interest was shown on phytochemistry³, and valuable research was carried out at Bangalore, Madras, Forest Research Institute (at Dehra Dun), Dacca, and Calcutta, etc., — notable workers² being J. L. Simonsen, E. R. Watson, J. J. Sudborough and their brilliant Indian collaborators. Simonsen (1910-1927) (in Bangalore and Forest Research Institute, Dehra Dun) carried intensive work on various essential oils isolated from a large number of *Gramineae*, *Coniferae* and *Compositae* species and elucidated the structures of santalene (the red colouring matter of Sandal Wood), myrcene, *d*- α -phellandrene, Δ^3 - and Δ^4 -carenes, *d*-piperitol, *d*-piperitone, *l*-carvomenthone, *d*- α -thujene, *l*-sabinene, zingiberine, curcumene, and longifolene, etc. He also established the structure of morindone and studied the composition of various seed oils from indigenous sources.

In Dacca, E. R. Watson (1910-1924) and his school published papers on seed oils and on the odorous and bitter constituents of neem oil. He also investigated the preparation of camphor from pinene and determined the pinene content of Indian turpentine oils. Watson studied the strychnine and brucine content of the seeds of *Nux-vomica* (*Strychnos nuxvomica* Linn).

J. J. Sudborough (1916-1927) examined a large number of essential and fatty oils from a wide variety of sources and established a relationship between the refractive index and the iodine value of a number of fatty oils from Indian plants. Sudborough and his co-workers investigated the production of caffeine from tea waste.

The Forest Research Institute at Dehra Dun did valuable work on timbers.

Under the auspices of the Lac Research Institute at Ranchi and under the guidance of G. J. Fowler (1915-1924) at Bangalore, a large number of workers studied the chemical composition of Lac and Shellac and helped to a great extent the industrial development in this field.

In the second quarter of this century, proper collaboration between botanists, chemists and pharmacologists was rendered possible for the first time and arrangements for clinical trials of the drugs were made by the establishment of a research hospital. This gave a great impetus to the development of phytochemistry and intensive research on the chemistry and pharmacology of plant products started in various parts of India in the following main channels:

1. Indian plants which have been recognised by the pharmacopoeias of various advanced countries as well as those which are being cultivated in this country.
2. Substitutes for pharmacopoeial drugs.
3. Plants used in the Indian indigenous system of medicine.
4. Poisonous plants.
5. Aromatic plants.

In the past two decades the research work on phytochemistry has received considerable encouragement through generous grants from the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, the Indian Council of Medical Research, the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, the University Grants Commission, the National Institute of Sciences of India, the Universities and pharmaceutical concerns. With the development of physicochemical methods, e.g., column chromatography, paper chromatography, counter-current method, ultraviolet, infrared, and nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, X-ray crystallography, mass spectrometry, and their applications in structural elucidation of organic compounds together with the spectacular advancement of knowledge on the biogenesis of natural products enriched by tracer technique, phytochemistry is making rapid and tremendous progress.

There is a great tendency in recent years among chemists to undertake this kind of work and much useful data on the chemical and pharmacological properties of the active principles of indigenous drugs have been furnished by many phytochemists in India. The C. S. I. R. has set up a Central Indian Medicinal Plant Organization and the Government of West Bengal has also organized a Medicinal Plants Committee of which Hon'ble Dr. B. C. Roy, the Chief Minister of West Bengal is the Chairman and under the direction of the Chairman and the Committee, cultivation of many important plants e.g., *Cephaelis ipecacuanha* Brot., *Ergot (Claviceps purpurea)*, *Rauwolfia canescens* Linn., *Rauwolfia serpentina* Benth., *Mentha (arvensis)* species, etc., has already been started. A plant survey in Eastern, Western, and Southern zones is being made by the Botanical Survey of India to collect a complete list of Indian flora for their studies on modern scientific lines with a view to making the country self-supporting by enabling her to utilize drug plants produced in the country. On the whole, it may be said that the trend of modern research is more and more in the direction of producing or isolating substances (a) which may have been of commercial or pharmaceutical value, (b) which may prove useful as synthetic intermediates or degradation products of more complex natural substances, or (c) which may help indirectly in elucidating the constitution of such complex compounds.

The active research centres where work on phytochemistry was done in the past and is also being carried out at the present are stated below with their major subjects of interest.

School of Tropical Medicine, Calcutta

Under the efficient supervision of Col. R. N. Chopra (1921-1939), a school on phytochemistry flourished in this Institution. Chopra with his eminent collaborators, viz., S. Ghosh, B. Mukherjee, N. K. Dey, and B. S. Kahali, made an extensive study on Indian plants with special reference to the isolation of plant products and their pharmacology. A survey of the work carried out in the School of Tropical Medicine has appeared in several books written by Chopra who is still pursuing researches on Phytochemistry in the Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu-Twai, and Kashmir. The books written by Chopra^{3a} also include a fairly complete bibliography practically from the time when phytochemical work was started in India.

S. Ghosh¹ studied several alkaloid bearing plants and isolated cardiac glycosides from *Nerium oleander* Linn.

R. N. Chakravarti^{4,5}, who succeeded Ghosh, has isolated a known sapogenin, diosgenin, from several species of *Dioscorea*. Chakravarti and his collaborators studied arborine^{4,5} (=glycosine), a quinazoline base from *Glycosmis arborea* and elucidated the structure of aegelin (confirmed by synthesis^{4,5}), an alkaloid amide occurring in the leaves of *Aegle marmelos* Corréa from which they also obtained γ -sitosterol. Chakravarti and his group in collaboration with Robert Robinson studied the constitution of echitamine and proposed a strychnine structure for this base^{3b} (cf. Ref. 16, 17).

University of Lahore

Research on Phytochemistry was initiated in this University by J. N. Ray (1928-1940). He did many valuable researches on the synthesis of isoquinoline alkaloids (Fam. *Berberidaceae*) and was the first to prove that vasicine⁶, the quinazoline alkaloid of *Adhatoda vasica* Nees, occurs in the family, *Acanthaceae*. This study has significant contribution on the biogenesis of alkaloids. Ray also studied the chemistry of rottlerin, the chief phenolic crystalline component of "Kamala". His latest contribution in the structural elucidation of chaksine, an alkaloid of *Cassia absus* Linn. which is still a confronting problem is really commendable. Besides these, Ray developed a good procedure for the storage of opium, the poppy plant extract and to prevent loss of morphine content and has prepared citric acid ferment from the lower plant, *Aspergillus*.

The syntheses of corydaldine and santene glycol by Ray have been considered to be "elegant". The synthetic experiments on oreoselone and other furo-coumarins have attracted considerable attention.^{6a}

University of Allahabad

S. B. Dutt (1925-1944) worked mainly³ on isolation problems and studied in a few cases the constitution of the plant-products^{1,4}. He investigated various plants, viz., *Aegle marmelos* Correâ, *Glycosmis pentaphylla* Correâ, Indian Kamala (*Citrus aurantium*), *Citrullus colocynthis* Schrad., *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn., *Lageneria vulgaris* Seringe, *Terminalia arjuna* W. & A., etc., from which many crystalline compounds (rottlerin, α -clatorin, mannitol, arjunin, etc.) were prepared and the properties of some of these constituents were reported. In 1945, he joined the University of Delhi where he continued researches in his own field till 1949.

Tibbi College, Delhi

S. S. Siddiqui (1928-1940) has extensive contribution in the field of Plant Chemistry^{1,3,4}. The main theme of his investigation was (a) isolation of active principles from medicinal plants, (b) studies on their pharmacological action, and (c) elucidation of the active principles wherever possible. He specialised on alkaloid chemistry although many sterols, chalcones, flavonoids and bitter principles from plants were isolated in his laboratory. The most important work for which he gained world-wide reputation was on *Rauwolfia serpentina* Benth and *Holarrhena antidysenterica* Wall. These plants were shown to be rich storehouse of therapeutically active alkaloids which have secured a good place in modern medicine. Work on the plants: Chana, Nimblossom, *Psoralea corylifolia* Linn., *Euphorbia tirucalli* Linn., and *Cassia absus* Linn, also deserves mention.

Siddiqui studied the constitution of pedicinin^{6b} isolated from *Didymocarpus pedicellata* R. Br, and assigned to it the structure (I).

(I)

University of Delhi

T. R. Seshadri who first initiated phytochemical work in Andhra University is still pursuing researches in the same line in Delhi University with a large

number of collaborators^{4,5}. His valuable and original contributions in the field of plant chemistry are outlined in the text, the main theme of which might be conveniently subdivided into the following groups:

- (a) Plant colouring matters belonging to flavonoids, anthocyanins, anthoxanthins, and chalkones, etc.
- (b) Lichens and mould products.
- (c) Natural coumarins (4-phenylcoumarins from *Leguminosae* family).
- (d) Biogenesis of flavonoids, coumarins and their derivatives.

(A) *Anthoxanthin glycosides and aglycones*.—This work was taken up by Seshadri with an idea to examine the correlation (if any) between the chemical composition and the botanical differentiation of the species and it appeared that there was. The investigation was started with members of the family, *Malvaceae*. He examined the pigments of the flowers of different species of *Gossypium* as also of *Thespesia populnea*, *Hibiscus cannabinus* Linn., and *H. sabdariffa* Linn. and later *H. vitifolius* Linn., and *H. esculentus* Linn.

(B) *Anthocyanins and anhydro-colour bases*.—A survey of plant sources included flowers of many garden plants, and forest trees, fruits such as the apple, lichi, jambul, pomegranate and chilies and agricultural plants such as the sugarcane and linseed. From these materials interesting informations were collected regarding the occurrence and properties of anthocyanins and anhydro-colour bases.

A recent study made by Seshadri relates to the components of the glumes of *Andropogon sorghum-durra* Linn. Two quinonoid anhydro-colour bases (Durrhodin and Durrarubin) have been isolated from these glumes. The former has been found to be the colour base of 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-4-methoxyflavylium chloride, the nature of the latter being a more complex one. Its properties and decomposition products indicate a flavylium structure with a trihydroxyphenyl ring attached to the 4-position. A comparison of the latter with a synthetic sample of 2,4-diphenyl-7-hydroxypyrylium chloride indicated their close similarity.

(C) *Leucocyanthocyanidins*.—In recent years, Seshadri studied the chemistry of leucocyanthocyanidins. (–) Leucopelargonidin has been isolated from *Eucalyptus calophylla* Kino. *Butea* gum has been shown to produce a (+) leucocyanidin, whereas tamarind seed testa (a large byproduct industry) contains another dextro-rotatory isomer. Their constitution still remains undetermined.

(D) *3-Hydroxyflavanones and catechins*.—The assignment of the dihydroflavanone structure has been ascribed to alpinone, fustin and ampelopsin. A number of such compounds has been found to occur in the heartwood and bark of trees, viz., pinobanksin, and taxifolin, etc. A detailed study of the association of flavonoids in plants showed that 3-hydroxyflavanones functioned as important intermediates in the biosynthesis of other flavonoids. It was shown by Seshadri that *l*-epicatechin occurs in a large number of Indian plants and has been considered to have vitamin-P properties.

(E) *Components of woods and related plant materials*.—Roots of *Decalepis hamiltonii* W. & A. and *Hemidesmus indicus* R. Br. were studied. They contain considerable quantities of triterpenes. *Derriis* roots belonging to various species were examined in the light of plant insecticides and some work was done on the constitution of scandenin and robustic acid. *Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb. was shown to contain a high percentage of pterostilbene which seems to have antidiabetic properties.

The study of the heartwood of *Dalbergia sissoo* Roxb. is of particular importance since it has yielded simple members of a new group of coumarins, viz., 4-phenylcoumarins.

Dalbergin (II) and methylalbergin belonging to this group possess substituents in the 6- and 7-positions.

(II)

(III)

(F) *Naturally occurring flavones and flavonol methyl ethers.*—Flavonoid methylethers, particularly their partial methyl ethers, widely occur in nature and have been found to have important physiological action, e.g., calycopterin has been shown to be an anthelmintic. Patuletin occurring as its glycoside was studied and was established as the 6-methyl ether of quercetegetin. Extraction of 'tambul' seed yielded tambuletin, first isolated by Bose (vide ref. 27) from this source. It was shown to be a monomethyl ether of herbacetin.

Besides these, Seshadri has considerable contribution in the chemistry of lichens (*Parmelia* species) and mould products. From the lichen *Toloschistes flavicans*, a colorless compound, vicanicin, has been isolated and shown to possess the structure (III).

Quinones, xanthenes, and chromones etc., have received his attention and the suggestion regarding the possible biosynthetic pathways of flavonoids, coumarins, furanocoumarins and chromeno- α -pyrones may also be recalled^{6c}.

Madras Presidency College

During 1928-1944 B. B. Dey studied coumarins and alkaloidal principles of several plants, mention-worthy of which are *Toddalea acculeata* Pers. and *Hedyrtis auricularis* Linn. The most interesting coumarin that he investigated was toddalolactone³ (IV) having hydrated isopentenyl chain in phenyl nucleus.

A brief account of the work of T. R. Govindachari on plant products carried out in the Madras Presidency College is stated below.

Of various plant products: (a) alkaloids of pyridine, isoquinoline, and phenanthridine series, (b) coumarins, and (c) terpenes, continue to dominate his interest^{4,5}.

Govindachari, (the successor of Dey elucidated the constitution of ethylcarpyrate (a degradation product of carpaine) on the basis of selective oxidation studies followed by synthesis. Gentianine, an alkaloid of *Enicostemma littorale* Blume (*Gentianaceae*), was shown to be 4-2'-hydroxyethyl-5-vinylnicotinic lactone. Recently he established the constitution of the complex alkaloid, tylophorine⁷ (V),

(IV)

(V)

the major alkaloid of *Tylophora asthmatica* W. & A. (*Asclepiadaceae*). The base has been shown to be 2,3,6,7-tetramethoxyphenanthro (9,10,6',7') indolizidin. The minor alkaloid, tylophorinine⁶, occurring in the same plant has been converted to dimethyl-2,3,6-trimethoxyphenanthrene-9,10-dicarboxylate. The constitution of a new alkaloid, reticuline, isolated from *Annona reticulata* Linn. has been established as 2-methyl-7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-1-(3-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzyl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline.

Tiliacorine, the major alkaloid of *Tiliacora racemosa* Colebr. was assigned the structure (VI).

(VI)

Besides alkaloids, Govindachari and his associates have studied the chemistry of a few bitter lactones.

A new member of this group, wedelolactone, was isolated from *Wedelia calendulacea* Less. (*Compositae*). From various degradative studies, it was shown that wedelolactone is the lactone of 5,6-dihydroxy-2 (2,6-dihydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-benzofuran-3-carboxylic acid. The synthesis of its parent ring and of its tri-*O*-methyl derivative were also achieved.

Another lactone, feronia lactone isolated from the root bark of *Feronia elephantum* Corréa, was identified as the geranyl ether of umbelliferone.

Mention should also be made about his recent work on echitamine^{9,10} and on jatamansone (a bicyclic terpene ketone from *Nardostachys jatamansi* DC. well reputed to produce sedative action).

University of Kerala, Trivandrum

The major interest of P. P. Pillay^{4,5} is centered around the domain of (a) essential oils, (b) terpenes, and (c) alkaloids with special reference to their isolation and characterization. The constituents of the essential oils of *Cymbopogon coloratus* Staff., *Cedrela toona* Roxb., *Anacardium occidentale* Linn., etc., were investigated and their possible uses were suggested. Among the terpene bearing plants, studied by him, mention may be made of *Pinus longifolia* Roxb. and Japanese *Mentha*. A number of alkaloid bearing plants, viz., *Holarrhena antidysenterica* Wall., *Strychnos nuxvomica* Linn., *Chonemorpha macrophylla* Wall., *Vinca rosea* Linn., and *Rauwolfia micrantha* Hook.f. were also examined by Pillay with a view to examining the nature of their basic components. Besides, he studied a number of complex phenols (from *Semecarpus anacardium* Linn.) and acids (from *Emblia officinalis* Gaertn.) for their commercial and therapeutic values.

Bose Institute, Calcutta

P. K. Bose, during his stay in the University of Calcutta (1934-1942) carried out valuable research work on phytochemistry. He is still actively pursuing research in his own subject^{4,5,11} at Bose Institute. His major interest is on (a) coumarins, their biochemical properties, (b) flavonoids, and (c) bitter furanoids. Bose examined the following plants:

Piper chaba Hunter, *Ananas sativus* Schult, *Eupatorium ayapana* Vent, *Aegle marmelos* Correâ, *Luvunga scandens* Buch-Ham., *Murraya exotica* Linn., *Glycosmis pentaphylla* Correâ, *Oroxylum indicum* Vent, *Phebalium argenteum* Sm., *Xanthoxylum acanthopodium* DC. *Blumea eriantha* DC., *Ferula alliacea* Boiss, *Didymocarpus pedicellata* R.Br., *Paederia foetida* Linn., *Aegiceras majus* Gaertn., *Heracleum concanense* Dalz., *Ficus* species, *Luffa cylindrica* M. Roem., etc.

He isolated 2,2-dimethyl- Δ^3 -chromeno- α -pyrone of angular configuration from *Seseli indicum* W. & A., 8-methoxy-2,2-dimethyl- Δ^3 -chromeno- α -pyrone from *L. scandens* Buch-Ham., and psoralene from *Phebalium argenteum*.

The constitution of gardenin¹², the flavone from *Gardenia lucida* Roxb., was postulated as 5-hydroxy-3,6,8,3',4',5'-hexamethoxyflavone or its isomer 5-hydroxy-3,7,8,3',4',5'-hexamethoxyflavone (cf. ref. 6c).

From *Mesua ferrea* Linn. P. K. Bose and D. P. Chakraborty have isolated a new 4-phenylcoumarin, mesuol (VII).

(VII)

(VIII)

Bose and Banerjee studied the chemistry of clerodin, the bitter principle of *Clerodendron infortunatum* Linn. (Fam.: *Verbenaceae*). Robertson *et al.*^{12a} as well as Barton and his collaborators^{12b} have shown that clerodin has the structure (VIII).

It was also shown by him that 7-methoxycoumarin possesses a strong haemostatic property and many natural coumarins exhibit remarkable antibiotic activities.

Bose during his stay in Lac Research Institute (1944-1954), studied the constitution of shellac and showed that butolic acid is one of its constituents.

Besides these, work on triterpenes⁴⁺⁵ is also being carried out in this Institute.

University of Dacca

During 1925-44 in Dacca, there were several active groups of workers³ of which mention may be made about S. S. Guha Sircar, N. K. Sen, J. K. Chaudhury and P. B. Sarkar. S. S. Guha Sircar studied the bitter principles of *Caesalpinia bonducella* Fleming, *Andrographis paniculata* Neés, and *Swietenia macrophylla* King. N. K. Sen examined the fixed oils and bitter principles of the seeds of *Corchorus olitorius* Linn. which possesses cardiac action. J. K. Chaudhury and P. B. Sarkar investigated the lignin content in jute and the chemistry of its cellulosic fibres where the cementing matters have been found to consist of polymerised hexoses and pentoses combined with uronic acids.

University of Calcutta

Work on natural products^{1,2,3} with special reference to natural colouring matters, essential and fixed oils, flavones and coumarins was initiated in this University by P. C. Mitter, M. N. Goswami (1928-1957), and P. K. Bose (*vide infra*).

Mrs. Asima Chatterjee has been pursuing researches in the field of Indian medicinal plants in this University for more than two decades^{4,5,13,14}. Her main interest is on (1) alkaloids belonging to the following series: isoquinoline, β -carboline, quinazoline, pyrrolidino-indoline, steroid and diterpenoid together with their structure-activity relationship, (2) coumarins, and (3) bitter furanoids. Chatterjee and her collaborators are the first to observe that, (a) β -carboline alkaloids of yohimbine series occur in the family *Apocynaceae*; (b) pyrrolidino-indoline in *Apocynaceae*; (c) Wieland-Gumlich aldehyde, i.e., Strychnine type base in *Apocynaceae*; (d) Simple quinazoline in *Rutaceae*; (e) Diterpene alkaloid in *Compositae*; (f) Indole-quinazoline base in *Xanthoxylum* species; (g) Steroidal alkaloid in *Chonemorpha* plants.

Several medicinal plants⁵ (nearly seventy) belonging to different botanical families (mostly *Apocynaceae*, *Rutaceae*, *Compositae*, and *Umbelliferae*) have been examined chemically. Some of these have eventually been found to be promising vegetable drugs, e.g., *Rauwolfia canescens* Linn., *R. serpentina* Benth., *R. micrantha* Hook.f., *R. beddomei* Hook. f., *R. densiflora* Benth & Hook., *Kopsia albiflora* Linn., *Alstonia scholaris* R. Br., *Chonemorpha macrophylla* Wall, *Vinca rosea* Linn., and *Aegle marmelos* Correã, etc. Most of these plants have received clinical application for their therapeutic efficacy. The alkaloids which were isolated for the first time and the constitution of which was established, are: rauwolscine¹⁵ (IX), rauwolfine^{15a} (X), serpinine (XI) and sarpagine (XII), belonging to β -carboline alkaloids having sedative and hypotensive properties. Besides these, she has examined various other *Rauwolfia* species of India and abroad from which a number of alkaloids, viz., δ -yohimbine and its congeners were isolated and studied.

(IX)

(X)

(XI)

(XII)

Kopsine (XIII), the strychnine-type alkaloid isolated from *Kopsia albiflora* Linn., has been shown to have curariform activity. Echitamine^{16,17} (XIV), which possesses an unusual skeleton and occurs in *Alstonia* species, has been shown to be an alkaloid of eserine

(XIII)

(XIV)

type which has been later confirmed from X-ray crystallography by J. M. Robertson^{17a} of Glasgow University. The occurrence of this heterocyclic moiety is observed for the first time in the family *Apocynaceae*.

The constitution of several quinazoline alkaloids, viz., glycosine (XV) (from *Glycosmia pentaphylla* Corrêa) and aegeline¹⁸ (XVI) (from *Aegle marmelos* Corrêa), has been fully

(XV)

(XVI)

established. It has been shown by Chatterjee and her research associates that rhesinine (XVII), rhesinc (=evodiamine) and rherine (=rutaecarpine) occurring in *Xanthoxylum rhetsa* DC. are indole-quinazolines by their degradative studies as well as by synthesis.

(XVII)

(XVIII)

The steroidal alkaloid, chonemorphine, a promising hormonal drug, has been isolated from *Chonemorpha macrophylla* Wall. The constitution of chonemorphine¹⁹ (XVIII) has been established from the degradative studies and also from its total synthesis.

A new observation has been made with *Inula royleana* DC. belonging to the family *Compositae*. It has been shown that the diterpene alkaloids, royline (=lycoctonine) and inuline (=anthranoyllycoctonine) occur in this family²⁰.

The investigation on the constitution of a new coumarin, marmin²¹ (XIX), as also studies on the stereochemistry and new synthesis of aegeline^{21a}, an alkaloid amide (both isolated from *Aegle marmelos* Corrêa) deserves mention. Bergamottin²² and a few naturally

(XIX)

occurring coumarins have recently been synthesised. Her researches in the field of lactones culminated in the elucidation of the structure of swietenine (XX) (from *Swietenia macrophylla* King; Fam. *Meliaceae*) and tinosporine, the bitter principle of *Tinospora cordifolia*

Miers (Fam. *Menispermaceae*). From I.R. and X-ray diffraction studies tinosporine has been shown to be identical with columbin.

Attention has also been drawn in the laboratory of Chatterjee towards the syntheses of naturally occurring alkaloids under "Physiological conditions". The synthesis of calycotomine²³ (1-hydroxymethyl-6,7-dimethoxy-tetrahydroisoquinoline) needs mention in this connection.

From *Prunus puddum* Roxb. ex Wall, D. Chakravarti and N. Kundu^{23a}, another group of workers, isolated puddumetin (flavone), prunasetin (isoflavone), and sakuranetin (flavanone) in 1949.

M. M. Chakrabarty and his associates of the same University are carrying on researches^{4,5} on the component fatty acids and glyceride composition of oil seeds of Indian plants, viz., *Cajanus cajan* (linoleic acid), *Citrullus colocynthis* (linoleic acid), and *Corchorus olitorius*, etc.

Presidency College, Calcutta

During the fifties R. Chatterjee carried out interesting work on Phytochemistry in Presidency College, Calcutta. His primary contribution was directed towards the field of isoquinoline alkaloids^{4,5}. He investigated several plants of *Mahonia* genus amongst which the following deserve mention. *M. acanthifolia*, *M. simousii* and *M. borealis*. These species were found to contain the alkaloids, oxyacanthine, berberine, neprotine, palmatine and jatrorrhizine. Umbellatine (=berberine) and neprotine (=jatrorrhizine) were obtained from *M. nepalensis* DC.

East India Pharmaceutical Works, Calcutta

P. Sen Gupta and H. N. Khastgir along with their collaborators have taken up an extensive research programme on Indian medicinal plants. Special mention should be made about the elucidation of the complete structures of two natural products, viz., nimbiol²⁴ (XXI) and psoralidin²⁵ (XXII). The constitution of nimbiol has received confirmation from the synthesis of its ($\pm$) *O*-methyl derivative by French²⁶ and American^{26a} workers as early as 1930 and later by Indian Workers^{26b} in the same year. The structural elucidation of

(XXI)

(XXII)

(XXIII)

(XXIV)

nimbin²⁴ by these workers is, indeed, commendable. Nimbin has been shown to possess either of the two partial structures (XXIII) or (XXIV).

National Chemical Laboratory, Poona

Under the supervision of its Director, K. Venkataraman,^{4,5,27} phytochemical work in N. C. L. is making rapid strides. Researches on three different sections of natural products are being pursued in this Institution:

- I. Natural Dyestuffs belonging to anthocyanins, flavonoids, and anthraquinones.
- II. Essential Oils of terpene series.
- III. Coumarins, flavones, isoflavones, and xanthenes, etc.

Research on Dyestuffs is being conducted by Venkataraman. From the wood of *Artocarpus integrifolia* Linn. several flavones, viz., artocarpin and isodehydroartocarpin, artocarpetin and artocarpanone have been isolated and their constitutions have been elegantly established. Artocarpetin has been proved to be 5,2',4',-trihydroxy-7-methoxy-flavone. Artocarpin has the same nuclear skeleton where 3-position is substituted by the group $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}=\text{CMe}_2$ and 6-position by $\text{Me}_2\text{CH}-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$. In isodehydroartocarpin, 3-alkenyl group and 2'-hydroxyl have undergone a cyclisation.

Two new flavonols, pinoquercetin and pinomyricetin, were isolated from *Ponderosa* pine bark and their constitution was shown to be 6-methylquercetin and 6-methylmyricetin. They are of special interest because only one C-methylflavone (strobochrysin, 6-methylchrysin) has so far been isolated from plants.

Isoflavones synthesised in Bombay laboratories by Venkataraman and his group were daidzein, formononetin, tectorigenin and muningin.

The physiological properties of naturally occurring anthraquinone and anthrone derivatives were also investigated. Morellin, the main colouring matter of the seeds of *Garcinia morella* Desr. has powerful antibacterial activity *in vitro*. Recent work has shown that morellin contains a 6-isoamyleno-2,2-dimethyl-5,7-dihydroxychromanone nucleus connected to a partially hydrogenated and alkenyl substituted naphthalene ring by an α -pyranone ring.

Essential Oils.—S. C. Bhattacharya in collaboration with K. K. Chakravarti and a group of active workers have been carrying on investigation on essential oils^{4,5} of santalol series, *Aquilaria agallocha* Roxb., *Saussurea lappa* C. B. Clarke, Indian dill oil (*Foeniculum vulgare* Mill.), Vetiver oil, Malabar lemon grass, and *Mentha viridis* Linn., etc. The structures^{4,5} of various terpenaceous compounds constituting these essential oils have been elucidated.

Zerumbone (XXV) isolated from the oil of Zingiber has been shown to be a monocyclic sesquiterpene ketone and the structure and absolute configuration of costunolide²⁸ (XXVI) from *S. lappa* has also been established.

Sukh Dev⁴ has studied the chemistry of terpenoids isolated from various essential oils and has recently made an important study on the proton magnetic resonance spectra of humulene, zerumbone and their derivatives. From n.m.r. data he has fixed up the precise location of the ethylenic linkage in humulene.

(XXV)

(XXVI)

Coumarins, Flavones, Isoflavones and Xanthenes.—From Indian flora several flavones and xanthenes were isolated by R. C. Shah^{4,5} (from 1934 onwards) and his associates. They obtained from *Oroxylum indicum* Vent., a 5,7-dihydroxy-6-methoxyflavone. Oroxylin-A, a companion flavone, was proved to be a 6-O-methyl-baicalin (5,7-dihydroxy-6-methoxyflavone). The constitution of calycopterin, the yellow colouring matter of the leaves of *Calycopteris floribunda* Lam. was considered to be a 4,5-dihydroxy-3,6,7,8-tetramethoxyflavone.

Swerchirin, a new xanthone from *Swertia chirata* Buch.-Ham. was proved to be the dimethyl ether of 1,3,5,8-tetrahydroxyxanthone. *Swertia decussata* Nimmo ex Grah., a plant which is used as a substitute for 'chirata' yielded decussatin and swertenin. From degradative and synthetic studies it was confirmed that swertinin and decussatin are the di- and tri-methyl ethers respectively of 1,3,7,8-tetrahydroxyxanthone.

Geigerin, a naturally occurring coumarin, was proved to be 7-methoxy-6-isovaleryl coumarin by its synthesis.

J. L. Bose^{4,5} of the same laboratory has established the identity of biochanin-A and biochanin-B (the isoflavones from "chana") with 5,7-dihydroxy-4'-methoxyisoflavone and 7-hydroxy-4'-methoxyisoflavone respectively. He has also studied the oestrogenic activity of biochanin-A and related products.

N. L. Dutta²⁹ of the same research institution has elegantly established the structure of munetone (XXVII), the active principle of *Mundulea suberosa* Benth. (Fam. *Leguminosae*).

(XXVII)

Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow

Intensive work on plant products is being done in Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, where M. L. Dhar and his associates^{4,5} have been carrying on researches on (1) alkaloids, (2) glycosides, and (3) saponin bearing plants as also on other miscellaneous natural products with the object of examining their therapeutic properties.

The structure of alangine-A³⁰ (from *Alangium lamarckii* Thw.) has been proposed to be 3-anisyl-2-piperidyl-*n*-propanol. Two alkaloids, hayatin and hayatinin were isolated from *Cissampelos pariera* Linn. Of these the former has been shown to be a bis-benzylisoquinoline base. *Cyclea burmanni* Hook. yielded an alkaloid identical with tetrandine.

From *Rauwolfia canescens* Linn., they isolated sarpagine and raunescine. The bases of *Stephania glabra* Miens were shown to be palmatine and tetrahydropalmatine.

The glycosides and saponins of the following plants have also received their attention:

Achyranthes aspera Linn., *Caesalpinia digyna* Rottl., *Centella asiatica* Linn., *Ailanthus malabarica* DC., *Erythrina indica* Lam., *Melodinus monogynus* Roxb. *Picrorhiza kurroa* Benth. gave two glycosides, kutkin, 6-cinnamoyl- α -D-glucosidovanillate, and kurrin, containing D-mannitol in the glycosidic portion. Besides these, various other crystalline components of varying degrees of therapeutic values have been isolated from other plant materials.

Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu-Tawi, Kashmir

R. N. Chopra^{1,4,5} and his collaborators, I. C. Chopra, K. L. Handa, L. D. Kapoor and others are studying extensively the flora of N.W. Himalayan region with special reference to the isolation and pharmacology of plant products. This work is mainly on the phytochemistry of (I) Poisonous Plants (Poisonous to Live-stocks and Human beings); (II) Essential oil bearing plants (Aromatic Plants); (III) *Dioscorea* species for the production of diosgenin; (IV) Toxicology of Indian cryptogams (or flowerless plants) and phanerogams; (V) Insecticidal and insect-repelling plants, besides various vegetable drugs as also their microbiological investigation.

Forest Research Institute, Dehra Dun

The chemistry of (1) Essential Oils, (2) Plant-pigments, and (3) Plants of established commercial (wood and other cellulosic substances) and therapeutic values are studied here. P. S. Rao⁴ and S. Krishna besides others are active workers in this field.

The work of S. V. Puntambekar and Sadgopal^{4,5} on the composition of essential oils and fixed oils, needs mention in this connection.

Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore

Studies on various essential oils initiated by P. C. Guha³⁻⁵ are still being pursued in this Institution by B. H. Iyer^{4,5} and his associates. In this centre considerable work on fixed oils isolated from various plant sources was done by J. L. Simonsen (*vide supra*) and P. R. Iyer.

University of Andhra, Waltair

The interests of L. Ramachandra Row^{4,5}, an active research worker in plant chemistry, (since 1950) centre round flavonoids, triterpenoids, and alkaloids. To his credit may be mentioned the isolation, characterisation and synthesis of three new furanoflavones from *Pongamia pinnata* (L.) Merr. and rutin from *Bauhinia tomentosa*. It was pointed out that the latter plant could form a commercial source for rutin. The peels of *Citrus mitis* Blanco. yielded hesperidin, 5-*O*-desmethyl nobiletin and two new flavanones, citromitin and 5-*O*-desmethylcitromitin. Citromitin was shown to be 5,6,7,8,3',4'-hexamethoxyflavanone and may be of considerable significance in the biogenesis of some *Citrus* flavonoids.

His examination of the local plants of *Menispermaceae* has resulted in the discovery of a new type of bis-benzylisoquinoline alkaloids with a diphenyl system. Row and his collaborators were the first to isolate tiliacorine and tiliarine from the roots of *Tiliacora racemosa* Colebr. and to show that they belonged to the new type of bis-benzylisoquinoline alkaloids. Trilobine was also isolated from the roots of *Cocculus hirsutus* Diels.

In a scheme on the chemical examination of the local timbers to explain the fungal and white ant resistance, 3-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone was isolated from the common teak, *Tectona grandis* Linn., and an entirely new triterpenoid from *Terminalia tomentosa*. By a systematic study, the latter was shown to be 19-hydroxy arjunolic acid. *T. arjuna*, *T. belerica* and *T. paniculata* were also examined. *Diospyros melanoxylon* and *Adina cordifolia* were also investigated under the above scheme.

S. Rangaswami^{4,5} has been pursuing researches in this centre primarily on flavonoid glycosides, lichens, triterpenes and related plant products.

The following plants were investigated:

Tephrosia lanceolata, *T. candida* DC., *T. hirta* Ham., *Usnea hirta*, *U. florida*, *Urginea indica* Kunth., *Entada scandens* Benth., *Parmelia tinctorum*, *Digitalis lanata* Ehrh., *Cerbera odollam* Gaertn., and *Ramalina farinacea*, etc. From *Rhododendron falconeri* Hook,

two triterpenes (ursolic acid and *epifriedelinol*) and a glycoside of quercetin (*hyperoside*) were isolated and characterised. "Maxima-substance-A" isolated from *Tephrosia maxima* Pers. has been shown to be a dimethylenedioxyisoflavone. Two crystalline glycosides, viz., *peruvoside* and *ruvoside*, from *Thevetia nerifolia* Juss., considered to be digitaloid glycosides, have been isolated. The constitution of *vogetin*, the pigment of *T. vogelii* Hook. was established as 6-methoxy-3,6,7,4'-tetrahydroxyflavone.

The phenanthridine alkaloid, *lycorine*, was also isolated by Rangaswami from *Crinum defixum* Ker-Gawl., and *Crinum latifolium* Linn.

Lac Research Institute, Ranchi

Major problem studied in connection with lac research⁴ is on the following:—

- (i) The constitution of lac with a view to improving its properties for industrial development.
- (ii) Preparation of good qualities of lac and its behaviour towards bleaching agents,
- (iii) Constitution of lac dye.
- (iv) Increase of production of lac from *Butea frondosa* Koen (Palas) and *Schleichera oleosa* Merr. (Kosum) by varying ecological and other factors.

An elegant review⁵¹ on Lac and Shellac has been published by the Indian Lac Cess Committee, Ranchi, wherefrom the detailed information on this subject would be available.

Plant Genesis

Phytochemical research done in the past and at present has divulged many secrets of nature: the properties of cellular constituents of plants, the characteristic features of many botanical families, and their biogenetic relationship. An outline of these studies* made so far is presented below and it will give an idea about plant genesis.

TABLE I
Alkaloid-bearing plants.

Family	Nature of the compounds studied.	Family.	Nature of the compounds studied.
Acanthaceae ..	Quinazoline	Chenopodiaceae ..	Naphthaphenanthridine
Amoryllidaceae ..	Phenanthridine	Convolvulaceae ..	(1) Piperidine-pyrrolidine
Anonaceae ..	Isoquinoline		(2) Indole
Apocynaceae (1)	Indole group:	Compositae	(1) Diterpene
	(a) Yohimbine type (α)		(2) Pyrrolizidine
	(b) Strychnine type (β)		(3) Pyrrolidino-pyridine
	(c) α & β types with several variants	Cornaceae ..	Piperidine
	(d) Pyrrolidinoinoline type (Eserine pattern)	Dioscoreaceae ..	Piperidino-pyrrolidine
	(e) Ibogaine type.	Ephedraceae ..	β -Phenylethanolamines.
	(2) Steroidal alkaloid(alkamins)	Euphorbiaceae ..	Piperidine
Asclepiadaceae ..	Phenanthrine-indolizidine	Fumariaceae ..	Isoquinoline
Berberidaceae ..	Isoquinolines	Gentianaceae ..	Pyridine
Boraginaceae ..	Pyrrolizidine	Gramineae ..	(1) β -Phenylethylamines
Cactaceae ..	Isoquinolines and β -Phenylethylamines		(2) Indole
Campanulaceae ..	Piperidine	Lauraceae ..	(3) Pyridine
Caricaceae ..	Isoquinolines		Isoquinoline
		Leguminosae ..	(1) Quinolizidine (Lupine type)

*"The Wealth of India" published under the auspices of the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research contains a comprehensive account of the results of work on plants.

TABLE I (contd.)

Alkaloid-bearing plants.

Family.	Nature of the compounds studied.	Family.	Nature of the compounds studied.
Leguminosae	(2) β -Phenylethylamine	Piperaceae ..	Piperidine
	(3) Pyrrolizidine	.. Ranunculaceae	(1) Diterpene alkaloids
	(4) Isoquinoline		(2) Isoquinoline
	(5) Bases with terpene moiety	Rubiaceae ..	(1) Quinoline (quinine etc.)
	(6) Indoles		(2) Isoquinoline
	(7) Pyridine		(3) Indole (and indole of α -type)
Liliaceae ..	Alkamines, phenanthridine ..	Rutaceae ..	(1) Quinazoline
	and colchicine type		(2) Alkaloidamide
Lineae ..	Piperidino-pyrrolidine		(3) Indolequinazoline
Loganiaceae ..	β -Type indole base (Indoline group: e.g., strychnine)		(4) Isoquinolines
			(5) Furoquinoline
			(6) Acridine
Lythraceae ..	Piperidine and dipiperidine	Solanaceae ..	(1) Pyrrolidono-piperidine (bicyclic).
Magnoliaceae ..	Isoquinoline		(2) Steroidal alkaloid (Alkamines)
Menispermaceae	(1) Bisbenzylisoquinolines		(3) Steroidal base with glycosidic unit
	(2) Isoquinoline		(4) Pyridine
Palmeae ..	(1) Pyridine		(5) Pyrrolidino-pyridine
	(2) Colchicine types		
Papaveraceae ..	(1) Isoquinoline		
	(2) α -Naphthaphenanthridine		

TABLE II

Triterpene, coumarin, bitter furanoid, glucosides, flavonoids, and steroid-bearing plants.

Acanthaceae	Dioscoreaceae	Leguminosae	Piperaceae
Apocynaceae	Ericaceae	Liliaceae	Rutaceae
Burseraceae	Euphorbiaceae	Malvaceae	Sapindaceae
Compositae	Ficoideae	Meliaceae	Simarubeae
Convolvulaceae	Guttiferae	Menispermaceae	Umbelliferae
Cucurbitaceae	Lecythidaceae	Oleaceae	Verbenaceae
			Zingiberaceae

TABLE III

Essential oil-bearing plants

Araceae	Cupressineae	Labiatae	Palmeae
Aristolochiaceae	Cyperaceae	Leguminosae	Rutaceae
Chenopodiaceae	Euphorbiaceae (also rich in fixed oils)	Lauraceae	Santalaceae
Compositae	Gramineae	Lythraceae	Thymelaceae
Coniferae	Guttiferae	Myristiceae	Umbelliferae
Cupuliferae	Fumariaceae	Oleaceae	Verbenaceae
			Zingiberaceae

Work on Indian Essential oils has been reviewed by A. K. Menon where the researches in this field by D. R. Dhingra, N. N. Godbole and others have been discussed^{3a} including his own.

This short review on Indian Phytochemistry is by no means comprehensive and, as indicated above, it is only a few of a number of topics in the field of plant chemistry which is being investigated in various active centres in India.

The work done on the medicinal, aromatic, and poisonous plants, the difficulties encountered and partially overcome during the investigation, and indications in regard to their utilitarian and scientific aspects will stimulate interest in this subject which is of great national importance. India possesses a rich and extensive forest resources, with varied types of vegetation as the dry deciduous, moist deciduous, moist evergreen, subtropical, temperate and Alpine. A survey of Indian flora, which is yet to be complete, has shown that India produces 11,000 botanical species of which only a few hundreds (nearly 600 species) have been examined. India's vegetable materia medica offers, therefore, a vast field of study and all that has been done to-date can be considered to have touched only the fringes of this vast and complex problem. Attention is yet to be paid towards poisonous plants occurring in nearly 90 families (belonging to both Cryptogams and Phanerogams) and aromatic plants which occur in 28 families. Particular care should also be taken in future on alkaloid bearing herbs because alkaloids are, generally, physiologically active and might turn out to be potent drugs in the therapy of many a malady. However, it must be admitted that with the growth of chemical laboratories in Universities, National Institutes, various Research Centres (National Cancer Research Centre, Calcutta, etc.), and Pharmaceutical Institutions, considerable progress has been made in exploring the potentiality of medicinal plants used in indigenous medicine. This work has brought out the merits of various Indian herbs which have secured a formidable place in world medicine. Importance of phytochemistry has been recognised not only in India but throughout the world because of its intimate relationship with medicine. From time to time, evaluation of this branch of chemistry is being made by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry by holding Symposia on the subject. The world scientists are taking great interest in medicinal plants of India, and research on indigenous drugs of late years has extended even to the western countries. A serious effort should, therefore, be made for proper development of Phytochemistry in our country which obviously needs collaboration amongst systematic botanists, chemists, and pharmacologists supplemented with requisite financial assistance.

REFERENCES

1. Chopra, Chopra, Handa, Kapur, 'Indigenous Drugs of India', U. N. Dhur & Sons, Calcutta, 1958.
2. Mitter, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci., India*, 1939, 5, 211.
3. Ghosh 'Progress of Chemical Research in India during the past twenty-five years' pp. 44-85 in Prasad's Progress of Science in India during the past twenty-five years, published by the Indian Science Congress Association, 1938.
3. (a) Chopra and Chopra, Review of Indian Medicinal Plants, 1955, published by the Indian Council of Medical Research. Chopra, Nayer and Chopra. Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants, 1956, published by the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research; Chopra, Bhadwar and Ghosh, "Poisonous Plants", 1954 published by the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research.
3. (b) (Mrs.) Chakravarti *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, No. 10, 10; No. 11, 25.
4. Annual Review of Biochemical and Allied Research in India (1950-59) published by the Society of Biological Chemists, India.
5. Proceedings of the Symposium on Phytochemistry, Kuala Lumpur, December 1957: Publication of the Unesco Science Co-operation Office for South East Asia. A Survey of Indian Phytochemistry,

- Part I. Asima Chatterjee, pp. 23-59. A Survey of Indian Phytochemistry, Part II. J. C. Chopra and K. L. Handa, pp. 60-74.
6. Ray, this *Journal*, 1958, **35**, 697.
 6. (a) Gaiind *et al.*, this *Journal*, *Ind. News Ed.*, 1939, **5**, 211.
 6. (b) Salooja *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1947, **6B**, 57.
 6. (c) Seshadri, *Tetrahedron*, 1959, **6**, 169.
 7. Govindachari *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1960, **9**, 53.
 8. Govindachari *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1959, 950.
 9. Govindachari and Rajappa, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 134.
 10. *Idem.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1960, **6**, 319.
 11. *Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1955-59.
 12. Bose and Nath, this *Journal*, 1938, **15**, 138.
 12. (a) Sim *et al.*, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 75.
 12. (b) Barton *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1961, 76.
 13. Chatterjee, *Fortsch. Chem. Org. Naturstoffe*, 1953, **10**, 390-423.
 14. Chatterjee *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1956, **13**, 346-443.
 15. Chatterjee and Pakrashi, this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 685.
 15. (a) Chatterjee and Bose, this *Journal*, 1961, **83**, 406.
 16. Chatterjee *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1960, 265.
 17. Chatterjee and Ghosal, *ibid.*, 1961, 176.
 - 17 (a) Hamilton, *et al.*, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 63.
 18. Chatterjee and Roy, Handbook of International Congress, 14 (1960): International Symposium on the Chemistry of Natural Products (Under the auspices of International Union of pure and Applied Chemistry) held in Australia, 1960.
 19. Chatterjee and Das, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1960, 290, 1247.
 20. Talapatra and Chatterjee, this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 437.
 21. Chatterjee and Bhattacharya (nèc Chaudhury), *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1922.
 21. (a) Chatterjee *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, **24**, 687.
 22. Chatterjee and Choudhury, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2246.
 23. Chatterjee and Adityachaudhury, *Naturwiss.*, 1960, **47**, 207.
 23. (a) Chakravarti and Kundu, *Science & Culture*, 1948, **14**, 36.
 24. Khastgir *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1960, **11**, 67.
 25. Dattagupta, Khastgir and Sengupta, *Chem. & Ind.*, 48, 1960.
 26. Fetizon and Delobelle, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, No. 9, 16.
 - 26 (a) Bible Jr., *Tetrahedron*, 1960, **11**, 22.
 - 26 (b) Ramchandran and Dutta, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 4766.
 27. Venkataraman, *Fortsch. Chem. Org. Naturstoffe*, 1959, **17**, 1-69.
 28. Rao *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1960, **9**, 275.
 29. Dutta, this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 165.
 30. Bhakuni *et al.*, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1960, **19B**, 8.
 31. Souvenir Volume on the occasion of Silver Jubilee, Published by the Indian Lac Cess Committee, Ranchi (1956).
 32. Menon, "Indian Essential Oils" published by the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, 1958.